

A HYBRID FEATURE SELECTION APPROACH USING WEIGHTED SCORING IN HIGH-DIMENSIONAL GENE EXPRESSION DATA FOR BINARY CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

Analyzing data with multiple dimensions presents a challenge for machine learning, data mining researchers, and engineers working with various forms of data like videos, photos, text, and voice. The high dimensionality of such data hinders decision-making processes. To address this issue, dimensionality reduction techniques, specifically feature selection, have gained significance. This paper introduces a novel hybrid method that combines the characteristics of the Random Forest and the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test. The proposed method consists of two stages. In the first stage, important features are identified using the Random Forest algorithm and sorted in ascending order of magnitude. In the second stage, the Wilcoxon Sign Rank method is utilized to select additional important features. These selected features are then combined to create a new hybrid model. The hybrid model utilizes the chosen genes to train the classifiers. To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method, six high-dimensional datasets are used, and its performance is compared against other feature selection methods, namely Proportional Overlapping Score (POS), Robust Proportional Overlapping Score (RPOS), Wilcoxon, Sigmoid Function (SigF), Genomic Clustering (Gclust), and Minimal-Redundancy-Maximal-Relevance (mRmR). The proposed method gives improved or comparable results to other techniques in most of cases.

Keywords: high dimension; feature selection; trees; wilcoxon; classification

1 INTRODUCTION

Dealing with huge data is a difficult problem for data science researchers in the modern era. When there are more features than observations, such as with high-dimensional data from pictures, gene expression, and next-generation sequencing, it might be challenging to implement classification methods since learning algorithms need a lot of data. The term "curse of dimensionality" is another name for it. Here, the number of observations is far less than the number of features, that is, $n < p$. Due to the dimensionality curse, such high-dimensional gene expression datasets are

often not considered good for classification purposes. Reducing the dimensionality of large datasets is one solution to this problem [1]. This issue may be dealt with by picking a reduced number of variables that can hold on to as much information as possible. In order to obtain a more acceptable learning performance, strategies are required to determine the ideal number of features [2, 3]. Gene selection is viewed as a feature selection issue in the context of machine learning, where the goal is to find a subset of the best discriminating features; see [4] and [5].

Wrapper, embedding, or filter approaches

are the three categories into which feature selection methods typically fall [3]. Prior to the learning process, the filter techniques rank the genes according to their relevance. Genes with better ranking scores are chosen for classification using filter techniques. Examples of these techniques may be found in [4]. With the use of learning algorithms that will eventually be used, wrapper approaches give rankings to genes based on their relevance. The technique given in [6] falls within the heading of “Wrapper methods.” In embedded approaches, learning algorithms and feature selection techniques are integrated to choose the most informative genes. The applicability of these feature selection approaches to other learning algorithms is limited by the close coupling between the particular learning algorithm and embedded methods. In [7], a thorough analysis of feature selection strategies utilizing feature modularization has been published. To choose informative features, these methods integrate a number of selection criteria with feature evaluation modules. As they execute quickly, these approaches are often used. Regression with LASSO, Ridge regression, and decision tree algorithms are some of the frequently utilized embedded processes. Random Forest [8] an ensemble learner based on randomized decision trees, provides information about feature importance. Random Forest is a set of tree predictors that can be used for feature selection. Microarray/genomic data analysis has been shown to be economical using Random Forest [9, 10, 11]. The research in [12] offers a Random Forest-based feature selection method that produces a set of low-cost features by taking the feature cost into account when building a base tree. The proposed strategy is tested using several UCI datasets because the likelihood of choosing a feature at random is inversely related to its cost. An improved Correlation-based Feature Selection (ICFS) combined with a Random Forest classifier is developed by [13] for discovering epileptic seizures from (EEG) signals. Initially, the ICFS is used to pick out the noteworthy attributes from the time domain, frequency domain, and entropy-

based features. A randomised decision tree-based ensemble learner called Random Forest provides information about feature importance. To choose the best discriminating features for cancer classification from gene expression data, the authors in [14, 15] have developed a hybrid feature selection strategy that incorporates the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test and Random Forest. By comparing the distinct levels of gene expression between cancerous and healthy tissue samples, the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test is used to determine the genes with the highest rankings. The significance of each gene in the context of the overall gene expression dataset is then taken into account by using the Random Forest approach to improve the feature selection process. According to the results, the suggested hybrid approach performed better than a number of different feature selection techniques, including those that relied on information gain, correlation coefficient, and t-test. A new Random Forest technique, known as RF, has been developed by [14] to identify the best characteristics while building RFs for high-dimensional data. The p-value evaluation method is used by RF to exclude uninformative features before choosing the subset of unbiased features based on various statistical metrics. Then, two subsets of this feature subset are created. The features from these two subsets are then sampled using a feature weighting sampling technique in order to construct a tree. The study in [16] has used a significant amount of data to evaluate Random Forest’s capacity to identify hotzones at the Traffic Analysis Zone (TAZ) level, which is a macro-level. A number of Random Forest models are applied via cross-validation approaches to determine the most influential macro-level crash risk factors. Wilcoxon tests are also used to uncover the distinctions of all features between hotzones and regular TAZs. It is also advised in [17] to incorporate the traits of two approaches while assessing their joint application of feature selection based on recursive feature removal, the Gini significance of Random Forests, and regularised classification methods. The use

of Gini feature importance for feature selection combined with a regularised classification through discriminant partial least squares regression demonstrated either comparable or superior performance when compared to using various univariate statistical tests or using regression coefficients within a backward feature elimination approach.

Although there are several methods for removing useless and insignificant genes from the data, each one has its own shortcomings. In order to address problems effectively, it is necessary to assess the effectiveness of uncorrelated removal in the commonly used feature selection methods. In this paper, we quantify the number of uncorrelated genes in microarray datasets, evaluate several methods, and develop strategies to lessen redundant data and improve classification precision.

1.1 Random Forest

Regression trees are used as the base classifier in bagging, and they are developed using bootstrap samples extracted from the training data. The outputs are then averaged

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code of a Random Forest:

Generate H trees

- 1: for $i = 1 \rightarrow H$ do
- 2: To create the i th bootstrap sample, choose a random sample of size n from the training data.
- 3: Create a root node called that contains the bootstrap sample.
- 4: all Build Tree(i).
- 5: end for
- 6: Build Tree(i)
- 7: If the root node includes every instance of a certain class, then return
- 8: else
- 9: Choose features at random from all the features in the root node.
- 10: Choose cutpoints X_{0p} and μ_{x0p} , the feature with the highest information gain, that best split the root node into child nodes.
- 11: Call Build Tree root node ($\leq \mu_{x0p}$); Call Build Tree root node ($> \mu_{x0p}$).

to get a single estimate [18]. For classification tasks, trees are formed on bootstrap samples taken from the training data, and a decision regarding the predicted class is reached by majority vote [8]. The enhanced variant of Bagging is called Random Forest. The following are the key steps of the Random Forest algorithm:

1. Create a specific number of bootstrap samples using the data.
2. Build a classification/regression tree for every sample in the bootstrap. The tree is built so that a random sample of features, rather than all the features, are chosen at each node for splitting, and this process continues until it reaches the terminal nodes.
3. New observations are analyzed by the trees before they get to the terminal nodes. A majority vote is used to decide on the class of the new data.

The pseudo-code of Random Forest is given in Algorithm 1.

1.2 Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test

One of the oldest and popular feature selection methods in high-dimensional datasets is the Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test (Wilc-RS) [19]. The following process is used by this technique to choose informative features.

$$w(g) = \sum_{i \in k0} \sum_{i \in k2} I((E_{i \in k0}^g - E_{i \in k2}^g) \leq 0), \quad (1)$$

here, class $k0$ denotes class 0 and class $k1$ denotes class 1. On the right side of the equation, I shows the discrimination function, where $E_{i \in k0}^g$ and $E_{i \in k2}^g$ are the expression values of the i th sample and the j th gene in classes 0 and 1, respectively. The discrimination function I is given a value of 1 if the statement in the bracket $(E_{i \in k0}^g - E_{i \in k2}^g)$ is true, else a value of 0. If $w(g)$ is close to 0 or close to the maximum of $n0n1$, where $n0 = |k0|$ signifies the total number of samples in class 0 and $n1 = |k1|$ denotes the total number of samples in class 1, the related gene is discriminative. The ability of genes to make decisions may be assessed by:

$$w(i) = \max(w(i), n0n1 - w(i)), \quad (2)$$

where $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, P$, represents the number

2 Proposed method

This paper introduces a novel hybrid approach based on Random Forest and the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test for binary classification. Random Forest and the Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test are two different techniques that are used for different purposes in data analysis. Intuitively, an ensemble of decision trees is used by the machine learning method “Random Forest” to produce predictions. The contribution of each feature in a predictive model is measured by feature importance. When a certain feature is employed for splitting in Random Forest, the impurity of the nodes in the decision trees is measured to determine how important the feature is. Random Forest utilizes the Gini index in classification to determine the best features by assigning weights to each feature. A higher Gini value indicates greater feature importance. However, there are instances when the Gini index assigns a high value to a feature that is actually unimportant or lacks significance in the data. To address this issue, we can incorporate an additional method known as the Wilcoxon Sum Rank test. By merging two feature selection techniques, we aim to increase the new hybrid model’s accuracy and precision. The Wilcoxon Rank Sum test is a non-parametric test and is used for feature selection in machine learning. This method assigns ranks to features based on the P-value. In this study, we propose to combine these key characteristics of Random Forest and the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test to develop a new hybrid method for feature selection. In the first stage, we use Random Forest to automatically choose key features and organise them in ascending order. To create an optimal set of features, important features are chosen using the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test in the second step. Then all the features generated by the Wilcoxon method are subtracted from 1 (i.e., 1 - important features) as the higher scores indicate greater importance. Finally, the important features chosen by both methods are combined to create new data. To assess the performance of the genes selected by the proposed method, the results are compared with six commonly used feature selection methods that are:

of genes in the training part of each data set considered in the study.

Proportion Overlapping Score (POS) [20], Robust Proportion Overlapping Score (RPOS) [21], Maximum Relevance and Minimum Redundancy (mRmR) [22], Wilcoxon Rank Sum test [23], sigF [24], GClust [4], and misclassification rates are calculated. Three well-known classifiers, Random Forest (RF) [8], k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) [25] and Support Vector Machine (SVM) [26] are utilised for this purpose in order to compare the performance of the genes chosen using the proposed method to that of other feature/gene methods. The suggested method’s algorithm is provided below.

2.1 The proposed algorithm

The steps involved in the proposed algorithm are as follows:

1. Divide the data into training and testing parts.
2. Train a Random Forest classifier on training data.
3. Identify the most important features by calculating feature importance.
4. Similarly, apply the Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test on the training data to identify important features and calculate the P- P-values.
5. Subtract probability of each feature from one.
6. Finally, weight Random Forest features importance by Wilcoxon probability and arrange features in descending order of importance.

Presented here is the pseudo code outlining a hybrid methodology that synergistically integrates Random Forest and the Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for the purpose of gene selection.

Algorithm 2 Pseudo code of the proposed method

Generate T iteration and grow T samples

- 1: **for** $i = 1 \rightarrow T$ **do**
- 2: Calculate features importance by Random Forest from the training dataset.
- 3: Now apply the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test.
- 4: Calculate features importance by the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test.

- 5: Weight Random Forest features importance by Wilcoxon probability
- 6: Arrange features in descending order of importance.
- 7: end for
- 8: Select the top required features.

Lastly, the top “ q ” features for the model development are chosen from $d(i)$.

2.2 Mathematical representation of the proposed method

Suppose the feature importance of each feature in high-dimensional dataset is denoted by $g(i)$ and p values of each feature by the Wilcoxon rank sum test is represented by $P(i)$, then the

proposed score $d(i)$ of each feature in the data is computed by the following equation:

$$d(i) = g(i) * (1 - p(i)) \quad (3)$$

The scores thus obtained in the above equation are arranged in descending order. The top ranked genes are then selected for the model construction.

2.3 Data

We use 6 benchmark datasets from publicly accessible sources to compare the performance of the proposed method to different machine learning methods. The types, features, and observations of the datasets employed are varied in nature. Table 1 provides specifics for the benchmark datasets.

Table 1 Selected Benchmark Datasets: For the classification tasks, specific datasets have been chosen. These datasets are structured with four columns: dataset names, the count of observations (N), the number of features (p), and the source of the data. The arrangement of the datasets follows an ascending order based on the number of features.

Datasets	N	p	Source
Tumors C	60	7129	https://www.openml.org/d/1107
Colon	62	2000	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/plsgenomics/index.html
Leukaemia	72	7129	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/propOverlap/index.html
DLBCL	77	5470	https://www.openml.org/search?type=data&status=any&id=45088&sort=runs
Adenocarcinoma	76	9869	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/propOverlap/index.html
Breast	78	4948	[27]

2.4 Experimental setup

In this section, we outline the experimental setup of our research. We have used six different gene expression datasets for our analysis, and each dataset is divided into training and testing parts, with a split of 70% for training and 30% testing. To ensure randomness and accuracy, we randomly selected 70% of the observations without replacement for the training parts and set aside the remaining 30% for testing. In order to assess the effectiveness of different gene selection methods and their associated classifiers, we conducted a split sample analysis consisting of 100 runs for each combination. The classifiers taken into

consideration for analysis were the k -Nearest Neighbours (k -NN), Random Forest (RF), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). For the implementation of RF, we used the R library “RandomForest” [28] with $nodesize = 1$ for applying Random Forest. For the implementation of SVM, we have used the R package “kernlab” [29] with default parameters. Similarly, we utilize R library “e1071” [30] with a default parameter value of $k = 5$ for the implementation of k -NN classifier. To select sets of informative genes, we focus on the training portions of each dataset. This involves employing various feature selection methods to choose sets of 5, 10, and 15 genes. The classifiers are then

trained using these selected gene sets. The performance evaluation of the classifiers is conducted based on the classification error rate associated with the chosen gene sets.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Within this study, we have conducted an evaluation of the proposed method and compared it against six commonly employed gene selection methods. To assess the effectiveness of these methods, we utilized six publicly available gene expression datasets. In this section, we present the results obtained from the proposed method. All methods are validated using the provided datasets (given in Table 1). To assess the performance of each method, we utilized three distinct classifiers: Random Forest (RF), *k*-Nearest Neighbors (*k*-NN), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The tables below showcase the results obtained from our proposed method (see, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7) below. For a comprehensive understanding of all the other gene selection methods employed in this study, please refer to the provided details [20, 4, 22, 24] and [31]. Table 2 presents the error rates for colon dataset by using 70% training and 30% testing data and selecting 5, 10, 15 features, respectively. The results are compared with other feature selection methods such as POS, RPOS, GClust, sigF, Wilcoxon and mRmR. The error rates in Table 2 show that the

proposed method outperforms to other methods by reducing the misclassification rate. It is notable that the proposed method provides lowest error rate in the case of SVM, *k*-NN and Random Forest classifier as compared to POS, RPOS, GClust, sigF, Wilcoxon, and mRmR. In Table 3, the proposed method is again producing best results for SVM, *k*-NN and Random Forest for the selected genes on Adenocarcinoma dataset. For DLBCL dataset, RPOS classifier is performing well on Random Forest and SVM while selecting 5, 20, and 15 genes, however, the prediction performance of Wilcoxon is better on Random Forest as shown in Table 4. The proposed method shows better or comparable results to POS, RPOS and Glust. As can be seen in Table 5, our proposed approach does well on the Breast cancer dataset when using Random Forest for selecting 5 genes, but RPOS outperforms when using *k*-NN, SVM and Random Forest. It is clear from the results that the RPOS method for Breast cancer dataset delivers better prediction accuracy. The results reveal in Table 6 that the proposed method outperform on Tumor C dataset as compared to all other methods in the case of selected feature i.e., 5, 10, and 15 genes on Random Forest and SVM. However, for Leukaemia dataset in Table 7, it is observed that for genes 5 and 10 the POS method shows plausible results by the Random.

Table 2 Classification error rate for Colon dataset with 70% training and 30% testing using three classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF), *k*-Nearest Neighbors (*k*-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM).

RF							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.386	0.370	0.284	0.242	0.334	0.196	0.196
10	0.392	0.341	0.281	0.254	0.293	0.211	0.184
15	0.389	0.357	0.247	0.244	0.303	0.211	0.179
<i>k</i> -NN							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.414	0.383	0.300	0.207	0.209	0.211	0.248
10	0.425	0.375	0.290	0.237	0.253	0.316	0.249
15	0.438	0.386	0.292	0.217	0.287	0.316	0.229

SVM							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.416	0.389	0.288	0.951	0.364	0.207	0.195
10	0.439	0.373	0.295	0.947	0.346	0.232	0.194
15	0.467	0.366	0.277	0.945	0.338	0.245	0.186

Table 3 Classification error rate for Adenocarcinoma dataset with 70% training and 30% testing using three classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM).

RF							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.207	0.317	0.218	0.319	0.412	0.312	0.181
10	0.453	0.423	0.312	0.312	0.480	0.390	0.178
15	0.219	0.230	0.309	0.230	0.403	0.303	0.178

k-NN							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.221	0.261	0.312	0.263	0.311	0.412	0.215
10	0.312	0.311	0.344	0.312	0.311	0.312	0.216
15	0.311	0.311	0.322	0.299	0.311	0.313	0.213

SVM							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.339	0.289	0.290	0.251	0.290	0.393	0.196
10	0.321	0.256	0.280	0.274	0.293	0.394	0.196
15	0.231	0.211	0.210	0.194	0.294	0.393	0.196

Table 4 Classification error rate for DLBCL dataset with 70% training and 30% testing using three classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM).

RF							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.212	0.223	0.312	0.257	0.205	0.318	0.144
10	0.076	0.114	0.073	0.252	0.023	0.285	0.120
15	0.074	0.106	0.107	0.191	0.039	0.270	0.101

k-NN							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.121	0.147	0.143	0.291	0.150	0.137	0.180
10	0.125	0.100	0.162	0.342	0.140	0.133	0.180
15	0.109	0.087	0.154	0.304	0.156	0.136	0.162

SVM							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	

5	0.153	0.117	0.185	0.337	0.252	0.261	0.144
10	0.093	0.073	0.092	0.258	0.257	0.251	0.177
15	0.100	0.047	0.058	0.176	0.275	0.250	0.100

Table 5 Classification error rate for Breast Cancer dataset with 70% training and 30% testing using three classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM).

RF							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.296	0.239	0.261	0.490	0.390	0.455	0.350
10	0.308	0.224	0.261	0.514	0.360	0.462	0.350
15	0.323	0.179	0.202	0.519	0.337	0.414	0.344
k-NN							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.314	0.206	0.313	0.448	0.405	0.402	0.424
10	0.276	0.240	0.297	0.501	0.390	0.396	0.389
15	0.297	0.204	0.241	0.514	0.391	0.401	0.393
SVM							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.310	0.260	0.512	0.522	0.384	0.367	0.398
10	0.272	0.214	0.522	0.484	0.351	0.456	0.386
15	0.262	0.215	0.515	0.462	0.350	0.427	0.373

Table 6 Classification error rate for Tumor C dataset with 70% training and 30% testing using three classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM).

RF							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.362	0.221	0.334	0.482	0.450	0.451	0.000
10	0.336	0.257	0.313	0.482	0.401	0.348	0.020
15	0.351	0.288	0.312	0.482	0.391	0.338	0.092
k-NN							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.423	0.269	0.383	0.407	0.398	0.396	0.438
10	0.332	0.220	0.355	0.471	0.391	0.395	0.412
15	0.293	0.242	0.344	0.415	0.382	0.386	0.420
SVM							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
	S	S	t		n	R	
5	0.362	0.264	0.333	0.277	0.442	0.373	0.039
10	0.341	0.242	0.336	0.302	0.396	0.349	0.077
15	0.312	0.249	0.311	0.228	0.400	0.351	0.098

Table 7 Classification error rate for Leukaemia dataset with 70% training and 30% testing using three classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM)

RF							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
		S	t		n	R	
5	0.003	0.032	0.040	0.171	0.050	0.241	0.010
10	0.002	0.036	0.029	0.173	0.021	0.215	0.011
15	0.006	0.043	0.025	0.156	0.040	0.223	0.000
k-NN							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
		S	t		n	R	
5	0.079	0.094	0.089	0.224	0.130	0.286	0.022
10	0.093	0.069	0.077	0.237	0.136	0.219	0.022
15	0.093	0.063	0.069	0.219	0.277	0.201	0.000
SVM							
Genes	POS	RPO	GClus	sigF	Wilcoxo	mRm	Proposed
		S	t		n	R	
5	0.067	0.055	0.076	0.166	0.070	0.257	0.022
10	0.075	0.046	0.133	0.159	0.046	0.241	0.022
15	0.070	0.043	0.137	0.166	0.061	0.219	0.011

In most cases, the suggested strategy outperforms the alternatives. This might be because combining the properties of Random Forest and the Wilcoxon Rank Sum test is a viable strategy for feature selection because it can utilize the benefits of both approaches. Random Forest is a widely recognized machine learning technique that can be utilized to select features by assessing the importance of each feature in predicting the target variable. When each feature is randomly permuted, the algorithm generates numerous decision trees and assesses the drop in accuracy. The characteristics with the greatest accuracy drop are considered the most essential. The Wilcoxon Rank Sum test, on the other hand, is a nonparametric statistical test that may be used to compare the distributions of two independent samples. It is based on the rankings of the observations and may be used to determine if the two samples differ significantly. The proposed technique can possibly uncover crucial qualities that are predictive of both the target variable and significantly different between two groups by

leveraging the properties of both methods.

To prove its efficacy, we have extensively tested the performance of our method on gene expression datasets and compared it to other existing feature selection methods.

Figures 1 to 6 provide a comprehensive analysis of normalized classification error rates for all the datasets using three classifiers: Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) across various gene counts (5, 10, and 15). The proposed method consistently outperforms other feature selection methods in most cases, particularly with RF and SVM classifiers. In the Colon and Adenocarcinoma datasets (Figures 1 and 2), the proposed method achieves the lowest error rates across all classifiers, highlighting its effectiveness in gene selection tasks. For the DLBCL dataset (Figure 3), the proposed method performs well with a smaller number of genes (5), while the Wilcoxon and RPOS methods show stronger performance as the number of genes increases. In the Breast Cancer dataset (Figure 4), RPOS consistently achieves the lowest error rates

in all classifiers and gene counts, demonstrating its reliability in gene selection. For the TumorC data set (Figure 5), the proposed method excels with the RF and SVM classifiers, while RPOS outperforms all other methods when k -NN is used. In the Leukemia dataset (Figure 6), the proposed method achieves the lowest error rates in most classifiers and gene counts, except

for the 5 and 10-gene sets with RF, where POS performs better. This detailed analysis highlights the overall effectiveness of the proposed method in reducing classification errors across diverse datasets and classifiers, while also recognizing the competitive performance of other methods in specific scenarios.

Figure 1: Normalized error rate of classification of different algorithms for Adenocarcinoma dataset. RF: Random Forest, SVM: Support Vector Machine, k -NN: k -Nearest Neighbor.

Figure 2: Normalized error rate of classification of different algorithms for the Breast Cancer dataset. RF: Random Forest, SVM: Support Vector Machine, k -NN: k -Nearest Neighbor.

Figure 3: Normalized error rate of classification of different algorithms for Colon dataset. RF: Random Forest, SVM: Support Vector Machine, k -NN: k -Nearest Neighbor.

Figure 4: Normalized error rate of classification of different algorithms for DLBCL dataset. RF: Random Forest, SVM: Support Vector Machine, k -NN: k -Nearest Neighbor.

Figure 5: Normalized error rate of classification of different algorithms for Leukaemia dataset. RF: Random Forest, SVM: Support Vector Machine, k -NN: k -Nearest Neighbor.

Figure 6: Normalized error rate of classification of different algorithms for Tumor C dataset. RF: Random Forest, SVM: Support Vector Machine, k -NN: k -Nearest Neighbor.

Boxplots of the data are also created in order to more thoroughly evaluate the effectiveness of different gene selection techniques. Boxplot shows accuracy measures such as sensitivity and specificity for 15 genes on the

k -NN, SVM and Random Forest classifiers using 70% training and 30% testing data. A sensitivity boxplot is used in statistical research to show how sensitive a model or dataset is to different input factors. Sensitivity

boxplots shown in Figures [7 9 and 11] may be very helpful in pinpointing the regions of a model or dataset that are sensitive to specific inputs, and they can also serve as a road map for attempts to improve or hone the model or dataset for improved performance. Where the whiskers extend to the minimum and maximum values within a given distance from the box, the 25th and 75th percentiles are represented by the box's borders, and

the median is represented by a line inside the box. Similar to a sensitivity boxplot, a specificity boxplot (shown in [8 10 and 12]) displays how changes in output values impact input variables rather than how changes in input variables affect the model's output or dataset. A model with high accuracy, high sensitivity, high specificity and low error rate is recommended to be used for prediction of class label.

Figure 7: Sensitivity for k -Nearest Neighbors (k -NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF) using 70% training and 30% testing data while taking 5 genes.

Figure 8: Specificity for k Nearest Neighbors (k NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF) using 70% training and 30% testing data while taking 5 genes.

Figure 9: Sensitivity for k -Nearest Neighbors (k NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF) using 70% training and 30% testing data while taking 10 genes.

Figure 10: Specificity for k -Nearest Neighbors (k -NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF) using 70% training and 30% testing data while taking 10 genes

Figure 11: Sensitivity for k -Nearest Neighbors (k -NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF) using 70% training and 30% testing data while taking 15 genes.

Figure 12: Specificity for k -Nearest Neighbors (k -NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF) using 70% training and 30% testing data while taking 15 genes.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a hybrid feature selection approach based on Random Forest and Wilcoxon Sum test for gene selection for dimensionality reduction. The proposed method combines some of the prominent

characteristics of Random Forest and Wilcoxon Rank Sum test to enhance the prediction accuracy. The results reveal that the proposed hybrid method gives an improved prediction accuracy by minimizing the misclassification rate. This study may be

expanded to include cases when the response variable is continuous in nature. The suggested technique may be applied to unsupervised machine learning scenarios as well. In these cases, the complete gene collection can be divided into several clusters, and each cluster can then use the suggested method to produce a set of distinguishing genes or characteristics [32]. The combination of the top-ranked genes in each cluster in this scenario will serve as the final list of discriminative genes. Moreover, by comparing the performance of the chosen genes to those of other classification techniques, the suggested gene selection approach may be confirmed [33, 34]. Nevertheless, the suggested approach's limited application stems from the fact that it is only intended for binary class issues. Also, in situations with extremely high dimensional settings, the procedure may become time-consuming. The use of parallel computing can be used to solve this issue. In future research related to this study, it would be beneficial to extend the experiments beyond functional genomics and explore other topics as well. Moreover, the application of the same concept can be extended to address regression problems. Additionally, it would be worthwhile to investigate different reliable metrics in order to develop effective filters for eliminating irrelevant features.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. C. Okimoto and A. C. Lorena, "Data complexity measures in feature selection," in *2019 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, pp. 1-8, IEEE, 2019.
- [2] Y. Yang and J. O. Pedersen, "A comparative study on feature selection in text categorization," in *Icml*, vol. 97, p. 35, Citeseer, 1997.
- [3] I. Guyon and A. Elisseeff, "An introduction to variable and feature selection," *Journal of machine learning research*, vol. 3, no. Mar, pp. 1157-1182, 2003.
- [4] Z. Khan, M. Naeem, U. Khalil, D. M. Khan, S. Aldahmani, and M. Hamraz, "Feature selection for binary classification within functional genomics experiments via interquartile range and clustering," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 78159-78169, 2019.
- [5] N. AlRefaai and S. Z. Al-Rashid, "Gene expression dataset classification using machine learning methods: A survey," in *2022 8th International Conference on Contemporary Information Technology and Mathematics (ICCITM)*, pp. 352-357, IEEE, 2022.
- [6] J. Chen, S. Yuan, D. Lv, and Y. Xiang, "A novel self-learning feature selection approach based on feature attributions," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 183, p. 115219, 2021.
- [7] A. Arauzo-Azofra, J. L. Aznarte, and J. M. Benítez, "Empirical study of feature selection methods based on individual feature evaluation for classification problems," *Expert systems with applications*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 8170-8177, 2011.
- [8] L. Breiman, "Random forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5-32, 2001.
- [9] H. Jiang, Y. Deng, H.-S. Chen, L. Tao, Q. Sha, J. Chen, C.-J. Tsai, and S. Zhang, "Joint analysis of two microarray gene-expression data sets to select lung adenocarcinoma marker genes," *BMC bioinformatics*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1-12, 2004.
- [10] C. Zhang, X. Wang, S. Chen, H. Li, X. Wu, and X. Zhang, "A modified random forest based on kappa measure and binary artificial bee colony algorithm," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 117679-117690, 2021.
- [11] C. Sinoquet and K. Mekhnacha, "Random forest framework customized to handle highly correlated variables: an extensive experimental study applied to feature selection in genetic data," in *2018 IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*, pp. 217-226, IEEE, 2018.

- [12] Q. Zhou, H. Zhou, and T. Li, "Cost-sensitive feature selection using random forest: Selecting low-cost subsets of informative features," *Knowledge-based systems*, vol. 95, pp. 1-11, 2016.
- [13] M. Mursalin, Y. Zhang, Y. Chen, and N. V. Chawla, "Automated epileptic seizure detection using improved correlation-based feature selection with random forest classifier," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 241, pp. 204-214, 2017.
- [14] T.-T. Nguyen, J. Z. Huang, and T. T. Nguyen, "Unbiased feature selection in learning random forests for high-dimensional data," *The Scientific World Journal*, vol. 2015, 2015.
- [15] A. G. Hussien, E. H. Houssein, and A. E. Hassanien, "A binary whale optimization algorithm with hyperbolic tangent fitness function for feature selection," vol. 2015, Hindawi, 2015.
- [16] X. Jiang, M. Abdel-Aty, J. Hu, and J. Lee, "Investigating macro-level hotzone identification and variable importance using big data: A random forest models approach," vol. 181, pp. 53-63, Elsevier, 2016.
- [17] B. H. Menze, B. M. Kelm, R. Masuch, U. Himmelreich, P. Bachert, W. Petrich, and F. A. Hamprecht, "A comparison of random forest and its gini importance with standard chemometric methods for the feature selection and classification of spectral data," *BMC bioinformatics*, vol. 10, pp. 1-16, 2009.
- [18] L. Breiman, "Bagging predictors," *Machine Learning*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 123-140, 1996.
- [19] B. Lausen, T. Hothorn, F. Bretz, and M. Schumacher, "Assessment of optimal selected prognostic factors," *Biometrical Journal: Journal of Mathematical Methods in Biosciences*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 364-374, 2004. O. Mahmoud, A. Harrison, A. Perperoglou, A. Gul, Z. Khan, M. V. Metodiev, and
- [20] B. Lausen, "A feature selection method for classification within functional genomics experiments based on the proportional overlapping score," *BMC bioinformatics*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 1-20, 2014.
- [21] M. Hamraz, N. Gul, M. Raza, D. M. Khan, U. Khalil, S. Zubair, and Z. Khan, "Robust proportional overlapping analysis for feature selection in binary classification within functional genomic experiments," *PeerJ Computer Science*, vol. 7, p. e562, 2021.
- [22] C. Ding and H. Peng, "Minimum redundancy feature selection from microarray gene expression data," *Journal of bioinformatics and computational biology*, vol. 3, no. 02, pp. 185-205, 2005.
- [23] B. Lausen, T. Hothorn, F. Bretz, and M. Schumacher, "Assessment of optimal selected prognostic factors," *Science Direct Working Paper*, no. S1574-0358, p. 04, 2002.
- [24] P. Das, A. Roychowdhury, S. Das, S. Roychoudhury, and S. Tripathy, "sigfeature: novel significant feature selection method for classification of gene expression data using support vector machine and t statistic," *Frontiers in Genetics*, vol. 11, p. 247, 2020.
- [25] T. Cover and P. Hart, "Nearest neighbor pattern classification," *IEEE transactions on information theory*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 21-27, 1967.
- [26] C. Liao, S. Li, and Z. Luo, "Gene selection for cancer classification using wilcoxon rank sum test and support vector machine," in *2006 International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Security*, vol. 1, pp. 368-373, IEEE, 2006.
- [27] S. Michiels, S. Koscielny, and C. Hill, "Prediction of cancer outcome with microarrays: a multiple random validation strategy," *The Lancet*, vol. 365, no. 9458, pp. 488-492, 2005.

- [28] A. Liaw and M. Wiener, "Classification and regression by randomforest," *R News*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 18–22, 2002.
- [29] A. Karatzoglou, A. Smola, K. Hornik, and A. Zeileis, "kernlab-an s4 package for kernel methods in r," *Journal of Statistical Software*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 1–20, 2004.
- [30] D. Meyer, E. Dimitriadou, K. Hornik, A. Weingessel, and F. Leisch, *e1071: Misc Functions of the Department of Statistics, Probability Theory Group (Formerly: E1071)*, TU Wien, 2019. R package version 1.7-3.
- [31] D. PEH, "Ro duda, pe hart, and dg stork, pattern classification," 2001.
- [32] E. Shamsara and J. Shamsara, "Bioinformatics analysis of the genes involved in the extension of prostate cancer to adjacent lymph nodes by supervised and unsupervised machine learning methods: The role of spag1 and plekhf2," *Genomics*, vol. 112, no. 6, pp. 3871–3882, 2020.
- [33] Z. Khan, A. Gul, A. Perperoglou, M. Miftahuddin, O. Mahmoud, W. Adler, and B. Lausen, "Ensemble of optimal trees, random forest and random projection ensemble classification," *Advances in Data Analysis and Classification*, vol. 14, pp. 97–116, 2020.
- [34] A. Gul, A. Perperoglou, Z. Khan, O. Mahmoud, M. Miftahuddin, W. Adler, and B. Lausen, "Ensemble of a subset of k nn classifiers," *Advances in data analysis and classification*, vol. 12, pp. 827–840, 2018.

